

Environmental and Energy Security Narratives around Liquefied Natural Gas in Dutch Written News Media

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Abstract—Media plays an important role in shaping public perceptions of technologies around the energy transition. We analyse Dutch written media reporting around LNG from 1991 to March 2025, focussing in particular on how its environmental impact is portrayed. We also examine which experts are most cited in Dutch written news media about LNG and their affiliations.

Since the invasion of Ukraine, Dutch media coverage of LNG has greatly increased, and narratives around LNG’s positive impact on energy security and energy independence have grown. However, LNG as a shipping fuel has been reported on for several years prior to that. In LNG reporting in general, but particularly in reporting mentioning it as a shipping fuel, the narratives positive about its environmental impact outweigh those critical of its environmental impact. In recent years, narratives critical of LNG’s environmental impact have become more prevalent.

There are a few prominent experts who are cited in reporting on LNG much more than others. Experts from an organisation active in lobbying or public affairs are cited more than those from an environmental organisation, and experts currently or formerly affiliated with a fossil-fuel-funded think-tank are cited more than any other organisation.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN ORDER to secure a liveable future, the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) stresses the need for rapid and far-reaching transitions across all sectors and systems [1]. The ongoing energy transition places growing pressure on incumbent industries to adapt. In response, these industries often promote climate mitigation strategies that preserve their business models while enhancing their public image. However, the solutions they propose do not always represent the most effective or fastest pathways to decarbonisation, and critical peer-reviewed assessments of such claims frequently appear only after a delay [2], [3], [4].

In such an environment, journalists are expected to produce independent, factually correct reporting [5]. They must be critical towards all parties and avoid even the appearance of conflicts of interest, while working under time pressure.

In this study, we examine to what extent narratives that align with industry messaging are reproduced in Dutch media, and how possible sources of bias can arise, by examining reporting into liquefied natural gas (LNG) in Dutch-language media in the Netherlands. In the Netherlands, LNG is imported and regasified for use in the grid, but is also used as a transportation

fuel, in particular for shipping. We therefore also examined reporting specifically about LNG’s use as a shipping fuel.

A. LNG promotion by industry

There are two main lines of promotion for LNG by the fossil fuel industry as integral to future energy systems. Firstly, LNG and fossil gas in general has long been promoted as a low-carbon fuel, since it typically emits less greenhouse gas than other fossil fuels per unit energy at the point of burning [6]. The narrative that fossil gas can be “transitional” or a “bridge fuel” towards hydrogen first emerged in 1994 [7], and began to be actively promoted by the fossil fuel industry after the financial crisis in 2008 [8]. For example, GasTerra (a gas company partially owned by the Dutch State, Shell and ExxonMobil) argued in 2008 for “Natural Gas as a Transition Fuel” [9] based on a report they commissioned from consultants CE Delft. The MIT Energy Initiative, funded largely by the fossil fuel industry [10], produced a report in 2011 promoting natural gas as a low-carbon fuel and a bridge fuel. Several authors and advisory committee members of this report had interests in, or were employed by, the fossil fuel industry [11], and the report was used by the US government to support their natural gas expansion at the time [12].

A second reason for the promotion of LNG as a pillar of the energy system of the future is its purported contribution to ‘energy security’. The International Energy Agency defines energy security as “the uninterrupted availability of energy sources at an affordable price” [13]. In particular the availability aspect has been a key element of fossil fuel industry messaging in recent years [14]. Following the Russian invasion of Ukraine in February 2022, fossil fuel industry lobbyists at the European Commission emphasised the EU’s vulnerability of gas supply while arguing for accelerated rollout of LNG infrastructure [15], [16]; Industry lobbyists’ public messaging presented investment in gas infrastructure as key to ensuring European security of supply [17]. In the US, oil and gas lobbies advanced energy security-based arguments for LNG expansion, both to the public and policymakers [18], [19].

European governments reacted to energy security concerns in part by expanding fossil fuel exploration and import infrastructure [20]. In the Netherlands, this led to a new an LNG regasification terminal at Eemshaven. According to the website of Gasunie, the co-owner, it was built “to increase energy security and reduce dependency on Russian natural gas” [21]. While no longer buying Russian piped gas, the Netherlands continues to import Russian LNG at the time of writing [22].

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B. Environmental impact of LNG

Although combustion of LNG by end users produces less CO₂ than coal or oil, methane leakage across its production, transport, and use chain is highly relevant to its overall environmental impact. The significant contribution of methane leaks, particularly during production and transport, to the lifecycle emissions of fossil gas (and shale gas in particular) has been known for a long time [23], [24], [25]. Nevertheless, these findings have been downplayed by the MIT Energy Initiative [26] and a study by the Sustainable Gas Institute (SGI) [27], an workgroup at Imperial College London which works closely with—and receives funding from—the fossil fuel industry [28], [29], [30]. Notably, the SGI featured in Shell’s Global Methane Communications Plan as providing “thought leadership and research into technology that could underpin role for gas.” [31]. In particular, methane emissions from U.S. gas production—the source of most Dutch LNG imports between 2022 and the first quarter of 2025 [22]—were found in 2015 to be significantly higher than estimates reported by the US Environmental Protection Agency [32].

More recent research in the Netherlands from 2017 show that “tank-to-wheel” emissions from LNG in lorries is comparable to diesel in urban driving, though they yield up to 20% less CO₂ equivalent in motorway driving [33], [34]. Research from around 2020 has shown that leaks from LNG’s use as a marine fuel have been historically underestimated [35], [36], [37]. A 2024 paper from Cornell University [38] showing that the greenhouse gas footprint for LNG from the US was greater than coal when considered on a 20 year time horizon was reported in media outlets worldwide [39]. In the Netherlands there was a lot of media coverage of the Advertising Standards Commission’s (*Reclame Code Commissie*) 2024 ruling that the claims of MSC Cruises’ advertising—promoting LNG as sustainable—were misleading [40].

Given this ruling and the centrality of methane leakage to LNG’s environmental impact, we were also interested in examining whether methane leakage is addressed in reporting on LNG, and how LNG is specifically framed when presented as a shipping fuel.

C. Role of the Media in Public Perception of Climate-Related Topics

Journalism is no “mirror to society”, but a selective account shaped by journalistic conventions as well as external pressures from parties with a vested interest in the topic. [41]. At the same time, news media have an active role in fostering public support for climate change mitigation measures, but as journalists themselves are not climate science experts, their representation of climate and related topics is influenced by their sources of information [42]. Resource-rich parties have a greater ability to access journalists and build relationships with them, to the detriment of resource-poor groups or those operating outside the political system, who will struggle to get their message across [41].

The role of the media in legitimising and amplifying discourses of climate science denial, doubt and delay is docu-

mented since the late 1980’s and continues today in the US and Europe [43]. A study of US news coverage in 1997 reported a pro-industry bias as well as misrepresentation of mainstream climate science. One of the contributing factors was that “Industry’s views ... were almost always given respectfully and at length. The newspapers of record repeatedly cited a tiny minority of scientists whose views happened to coincide with those of the oil, coal, auto, and petrochemical industries” [44].

In Germany, Poland and Czechia the dominant voices in print media coverage of coal in 2015-16 were politicians and industry [45]; narratives are dominated by countries’ governments’ political agenda. While climate protection appears in German media narratives (and is also a significant political priority in Germany), climate change is minimised in Polish media and omitted in Czech media. The authors conclude that “the media act mainly as a platform for the countries’ decision makers and energy policy stakeholders to voice their perspectives”.

Journalistic lack of expertise in the topic at hand, too, lead to reporting where some perspectives are underrepresented. Kleinberga et al. [46] describe a simplification and fragmentation of narratives around climate change in Latvian media, *inter alia*, that the effects of climate change are reported on but a link is not made to the actors causing it. They note that inexperience of reporters with the topic of climate change leads to global news being taken over but not linked to local context or local prevalent discourses, which might engage readers and offer them a positive, transformative perspective.

Another important class of actor interacting with the media are policy think tanks, which “do not just, or even primarily, exist to provide evidence” but rather provide support for particular causes and world views [47]. In the UK, the Global Warming Policy Foundation and Net Zero Watch promulgated erroneous claims about renewable energy in UK media [43, Ch. 2]. Industry-funded research institutes in Germany are responsible for pro-fossil-fuel discourse in German media [43, Ch. 6]

Taken together, the experts, organisations, and news sources that journalists rely upon determine the extent of public (mis)understanding of topics related to climate change and energy policy.

II. METHODOLOGY

We explain the methodology used in the analysis of LNG news articles. We explain the choice of narratives below, how the corpus was identified, and how we used search strings to help identify the relevant narratives and experts cited in the articles.

A. Breakdown and Choice of Narratives

We searched for specific narratives related to LNG in industry press releases e.g. [48], critical reports from advocates against LNG e.g. [49] and news articles, to build up a preliminary taxonomy – which we do not claim to be exhaustive – of narratives around LNG. We also added to this taxonomy during the coding process (Sec. II-D), i.e. to include narratives that we had missed.

These narratives were grouped in the taxonomy into broader sets of narratives: Firstly into whether they were LNG-positive (+), LNG-critical (-) or LNG-neutral (*), and then whether they were to do with environment (E), (geo)politics including energy security (G), innovation (I), pragmatism including price of gas (P), safety and legality (S) or ethics (T). An overview of the narrative taxonomy is in Appendix A.

Given the size of the dataset, it would have been infeasible to code all these narratives. We chose to focus our analysis on the following narrative sets:

- E+ Narratives positive about LNGs impact on the environment;
- E- Narratives critical of LNGs impact on the environment;
- G+ Narratives suggesting that LNG can contribute to security or independence of energy supply.

We chose environmental narratives E+ and E- because the environmental impact of LNG is both a point of fossil fuel industry public relations as well as an evolving research topic in the last 15 years. We were interested in G+ since gas was promoted as a contributor to energy security by industry following the invasion of Ukraine, as mentioned in Sec. I-A.

B. Identifying the corpus

The corpus was put together by searching Nexis Uni¹ for Dutch-language news articles with the search term *vloeibaar gas* (liquefied gas - the term for both LNG, liquefied natural gas and LPG, liquefied petroleum gas). We also searched the NOS website for the same term *vloeibaar gas* and downloaded all of these articles. The articles dated from 1991 to 26 March 2025.

Using the non-case-sensitive search strings such as “LPG” and “autogas” (common names for liquefied petroleum gas) we found articles that were not about LNG and excluded them. Some articles talk about liquefied natural gas but mistakenly call it LPG - these are included in the corpus.

We also excluded opinion pieces, as far as this could be determined from the text. We did this by excluding articles from which the title was “Lezersbrieven”, “Lezersreacties”, “Opinie” and “Het Rubriek U” and also searching the body of the articles for the non-case-sensitive search strings indicating that they were opinion pieces, and excluding those which were obvious opinion pieces. This is because we are interested in analysing the journalistic choices of the newspaper, i.e. columnists and reporters, and not the opinion editorial desk. A full list of search strings used to exclude irrelevant articles is in Appendix C.

C. Filtering News Outlets

We decided to use articles from national and regional newspapers based in the Netherlands as well as weekly opinion magazines, lifestyle magazines, the websites of the aforementioned,

and the news websites NOS and nu.nl. We excluded trade journals. A full list of the news outlets used is in Appendix B. This yielded a total corpus size of 9159.

D. Coding articles with narratives

A challenge was to code the large number of articles with the chosen narratives. As explained in Sec. I, we focussed on environmental narratives (LNG-positive and LNG-critical) and energy security narratives.

A number of articles appear multiple times with identical text or only minor differences, mostly in formatting. This occurs, for example, when an article was reposted on the online paper or the weekend edition, or an outlet reused a text published elsewhere. To make the coding more efficient, such articles were grouped together and the text from one article used for analysis; the analysis was then applied to all articles with this text. Comparisons of the similarity of the text were made with the `SequenceMatcher` function from the `difflib` python module, which uses the Ratcliff/Obershelp algorithm [50] and yields a value between 0 and 1, with 1 being a perfect match. We used a threshold of 0.8 to determine if two articles were similar enough to be coded together. This gave us 4484 individual texts to be analysed.

To simplify this further, we searched for words and phrases related to the narratives and excluded those article texts not containing any of these words and phrases. We used a large amount of words to minimise as much as possible the risk of excluding an article containing a narrative (i.e., a false negative). Then a human coder reviewed the only the articles containing these search strings, manually, to eliminate false positives (only one coder did the coding, hence no intercoder reliability test was needed). We sped up the process of coding by highlighting the immediate context of these keywords and phrases. This way, only the relevant sentences or paragraphs needed to be read, if the context was unambiguous. The exact search strings used are in Appendix C, as are the instructions for coding.

We also used this method to identify articles which mention LNG as a shipping fuel, and articles which explicitly mention methane leaks. The keywords used are found in Appendix C.

E. Identifying experts cited

To determine which experts were consulted or cited, we searched for the phrases “*expert*”, “*deskundig*”, “*zegt*”, “*volgens*” and “*aldus*” which are words for “expert”, “says”, and “according to” in Dutch. We manually identified which names belonged together (as the same person; for example, Coby van der Linde might be referred to by her full name but also as “Professor van der Linde”, “C. van der Linde” or “energy expert van der Linde”). We then identified which article texts included a mention of these names. We excluded in our definition of expert: politicians, government officials, public figures, or people who were only representing a fossil fuel company or an LNG-importing port. With fossil fuel company, we mean a company involved in exploration, production, transport and

¹Nexis Uni is a paid-subscription database of news articles. See: <https://www.lexisnexis.com/en-us/professional/academic/nexis-uni.page>

Fig. 1: Number of articles about LNG per year since 1991 (2025 only until March 26)

Fig. 2: Number of articles where LNG is referred to as a shipping fuel, per year since 1991 (2025 only until March 26)

storage of fossil fuels, including liquefaction/regassing of LNG (upstream or midstream activities). Companies only involved in end-user distribution or who use fossil fuel feedstocks (downstream activities) are out of scope.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

LNG began to be increasingly reported on by Dutch news media around 2004, see Fig. 1. In 2011 the first LNG terminal opened in Rotterdam and the first imports were registered in 2012 [22]. In 2022 there was a spike in news coverage, and the Netherlands opened a second LNG regasification facility in Eemshaven, according to Gasunie, to “increase energy security and reduce dependence on Russian natural gas”[21].

Over the whole time period, 2519 articles (28% of corpus) contained a positive geopolitical narrative and 1311 (14%) contained an environmental narrative (Fig. 3). Of these, 834, (9%) contained an environmental narrative positive about LNG and 582 (6%) contained an environmental narrative critical of LNG (Fig. 4).

In the following subsections, we look at how these narratives changed over time, whether there were differences per news outlet, what trends could be found within articles specifically mentioning LNG as a shipping fuel, and how many articles

Fig. 3: Breakdown of narratives: G+ (black) and environmental (i.e. E+ and E-, green)

mentioned leakage of methane. We also looked at the expert voices cited and their frequency of appearance.

A. Change in narratives through time

Of the 834 articles with a LNG-positive environmental narrative (E+), around half (375) contained the narrative “LNG is a transition fuel” (E2 in the taxonomy in Appendix A)

582 articles (6% of the corpus) contained an LNG-critical narrative, of which around a quarter (134) contained the

Fig. 4: Breakdown of narratives: E+ (yellow) and E- (pink)

Fig. 5: Frequency of articles with an environmental narrative, by whether they contain an LNG-positive (E+) or LNG-critical (E-) narrative, or both, from 2011 to March 2025

narrative “LNG is not a transition fuel” (E6 in the taxonomy in Appendix A). See Fig. 4 for the breakdown of positive and critical environmental narratives in the entire corpus. Fig. 5 shows articles with an environmental narrative since 2011 and their breakdown into articles with E+ and articles with E- narratives. Fig. 6 shows articles which mention LNG as a transition fuel since 2011, and their breakdown into E2 (LNG is a transition fuel) and E6 (LNG is not a transition fuel).

A shift can be seen towards more environmental-critical narratives since 2022. As mentioned in Sec. I-B, there has been increasing criticism of LNG’s environmental impact in recent years from academic research and public bodies, which is reflected in Dutch media. However, articles referring to LNG as “clean” (*schoon*) persist into 2025. Of all articles in 2022 or later which contain an environmental narrative, 18% contain *only* narratives positive about LNG’s environmental impact (i.e., no LNG-critical environmental narratives). Before 2022, however, this figure was 84%.

Positive geopolitical narratives (G+) saw an increase from 2022 onwards - 11% of articles before 2022 had a G+ narrative compared with 41% of articles in 2022 and later.

B. Breakdown by News Outlet

There was some variation between news outlets. Looking at four popular print media publications, for example: environmental narratives (E+ and E-) were 19% and 14% of articles in the left-of-centre² newspapers *Trouw* and *NRC*, compared

²See: <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com/nrc-bias/> and <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com/trouw-bias/>

Fig. 6: Frequency of articles with a narrative about LNG as a transition fuel, by whether they contain a narratives supporting LNG being viewed as a transition fuel (E2), or contradicting this (E6), or both, from 2011 to March 2025

Fig. 7: Breakdown of articles in *Trouw* (left) and *de Volkskrant* (right) by whether they contain an environmental or energy security narrative

to 9% of right-of-centre³ *de Volkskrant* and 8% of right-wing⁴ *De Telegraaf*. See Fig. 7 for a comparison of two outlets.

We performed a χ^2 test on the number of articles with and without an environmental narrative for each of these newspapers. The differences were significant ($p < 0.05$) between all newspapers except between *de Volkskrant* and *De Telegraaf*, and highly significant ($p < 0.001$) between *Trouw* and *de Volkskrant* ($\chi^2 = 20, p < 0.0001$), *Trouw* and *De Telegraaf* ($\chi^2 = 39, p < 0.0001$), and between *NRC* and *De Telegraaf* ($\chi^2 = 13.7, p = 0.0002$). There were no significant differences in the frequency of articles with geopolitical (G+) narratives between any of these outlets.

C. LNG as a shipping fuel

5.5% of all articles (506 articles) referred to LNG as a shipping fuel. Of this subset, 77% (388 articles) contained E+ narratives, 16% (81 articles) contained E- narratives, and 14% (71 articles) contained G+ narratives. See Fig. 8

Looking more closely at E+ narratives in this subset, 66% (332 articles) contained E+ but no E- narratives (e.g. referred to LNG as a clean fuel and did not mention negative environmental impacts). See Fig. 9. For comparison, only 8% of the whole corpus (729 articles) contains E+ but no E- narratives.

Articles mentioning LNG as a shipping fuel peaked slightly in 2015, see Fig. 2. Since 2020, more LNG-critical environmental narratives (E-) are seen, see Fig. 10. Many of these reference recent research critical of LNG’s climate impact or the ruling

³See: <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com/de-volkskrant/>

⁴See: <https://mediabiasfactcheck.com/de-telegraaf/>

Fig. 8: Breakdown of articles where LNG is referred to as a shipping fuel, by whether they contain an environmental or energy security narrative

Fig. 9: Breakdown of articles where LNG is referred to as a shipping fuel, by whether they contain an E+ or E- narrative

Fig. 10: Frequency of articles where LNG is referred to as a shipping fuel, by whether they contain an E+ (yellow) or E- (magenta) narrative, both (light pink), or neither (grey), from 2011 to March 2025

of the Dutch Advertising Standards Commission against MSC Cruises [40].

D. Mention of methane leaks

Looking at articles which contain narratives about the environment (E+ and E-), 9.4% (123 out of 1311) mention the leakage of methane. This does not increase when looking at the subset of articles with an environmental narrative which also mention LNG as a shipping fuel: around 8.5% (35 out of 413) of these mention methane leaks.

E. Cited voices and organisations

We identified the experts cited and the number of articles in which they were cited as detailed in Sec. II-E. The most cited

Fig. 11: Experts and the amount of articles in which they are cited. On the left of the figure: In yellow are experts affiliated with the CIEP, magenta designates affiliation with a lobby representing fossil fuel companies or public affairs firm with fossil fuel clientele. The remainder (black) have other affiliations. Hatching designates former affiliation during the period of study; dots mean that part of the articles were from before the person was affiliated with the organisation. On the right of the figure, in green, are the most cited experts belonging to an environmental organisation.

experts in the corpus are shown in Fig. 11.

The organisations with the most cited experts (excluding fossil fuel companies, the port, governmental organisations and political parties) are the Centre for International Energy Policy (CIEP, 686 articles featuring people currently or formerly affiliated with it), The Hague Centre for Strategic Studies (HCSS, 511 articles) and Netherlands Organisation for Applied Scientific Research (TNO, 411 articles)

The CIEP has its roots in the Clingendael International Energy Programme (also called CIEP), although the CIEP no longer is affiliated with the Clingendael Institute [51]. According to their website [52] they are supported by public and private stakeholders; according to their 2024 annual report these "stakeholder contributions" comprise most of their income. From the 24 "supporting institutions", 18 are active in the production or transport of gas, or operate gas-fired power plants [53].

The top 3 most cited experts from an environmental organisation have 114 articles between them. They are Mark van Baal from Follow This, Marjan Minnesma from Urgenda, and Donald Pols from Milieudefensie (Friends of the Earth Netherlands). The three most heavily featured experts from a lobbying organisation, defined as lobbies representing (inter alia) fossil fuel industry, or public affairs organisations which have a fossil fuel industry client, are cited in 159 articles between them. These are Hans van Cleef who worked (from 2023 until the end of the time period studied) at *Publieke Zaken*, a company offering services in "public affairs consulting, strategy and execution" [54], [55] with ENGIE as one of its clients [56]; Hans Grünfeld from *Vereniging voor Energie, Milieu en Water* (VEMW) and Ingrid Thijssen from VNO-NCW, both lobbies representing—among others—the gas

industry. Note: we count Hans van Cleef's articles only from 2023 onwards, since before he was not at Publieke Zaken [57].

The most-cited expert, Martien Visser, had a position at the Hanzehogeschool Groningen, but was, until the end of the time period studied, Manager Corporate Strategy at Gasunie [58], [59]. Of the 348 of the articles in which he is mentioned, his Gasunie position is mentioned in only 18% of them (63 articles) and a connection to Gasunie in another 2% (6 articles). In the rest of the articles (80%, 279 articles) no affiliation with Gasunie is mentioned, even if a spokesperson for the company is also quoted in the same article.

Some experts are or were affiliated with a university or higher education institute, but also have connections to the CIEP. The most cited are:

- Martien Visser (2012-April 2025 professor at the Hanzehogeschool Groningen, 2013-2016 and 2017-April 2025 Manager Corporate Strategy, Gasunie[58], [59]; He is mentioned as an Associate Fellow (project basis) at CIEP in its annual reports [53] and on the website, but was not active between 2012 and April 2025 [60] Since his retirement he is active again with the CIEP, see e.g.[61]; 348 articles)
- Aad Correljé (TU Delft, Associate Fellow (project basis) at CIEP[53]; 114 articles)
- Coby van der Linde (formerly Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, director CIEP until 2024, after which senior fellow at CIEP [53], [51]; 68 articles)

Other experts at universities receive incidental funding from the fossil fuel industry. The most cited in our corpus are Machiel Mulder, Professor of Energy Economics at Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, who worked on research financed by GasTerra (e.g. [62]), and also on a policy paper commissioned by Shell's lawyers and financed by Shell [63], [64]; (94 articles) and Jan Rotmans at Erasmus University Rotterdam, who has advised for Shell [65] (34 articles)⁵.

Note that we do not evaluate which narratives appear in the contributions of the experts, nor the content of these contributions. We also do not insinuate that the experts quoted spread incorrect information or speak outside of their area of expertise. We simply highlight the voices most cited in articles about LNG and their affiliations, including varying degrees of connection to the fossil fuel industry.

F. Limitations

A limitation of this study is that we only coded whether narratives appeared in an article and not to whom the narratives are attributed. Links between actors and narratives are therefore beyond the scope of this study.

Another limitation of this study is that we only focussed on narratives which coincide with industry messaging (G+ and E+) and those critical of LNG's environmental impact

⁵All persons whose affiliations were mentioned in the text were contacted with a draft of this manuscript to ensure these affiliations were correct, but not all responded.

(E-). In order to compare geopolitical narratives as we did environmental narratives, it would be necessary to include negative geopolitical narratives (G-). Hence, in this study we cannot draw conclusions as to whether the narrative of energy security and energy independence was generally presented with or without a counternarrative.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

Our study of Dutch media articles around LNG can provide insight into how media react to technological, scientific and geopolitical developments, and their role in enabling or preventing obstruction of effective climate mitigation.

Examining the Dutch media coverage of LNG, we find:

- Focus on LNG as a news topic peaked in 2022. Narratives about energy security and energy independence experienced a sharp increase at this period (11% of articles before 2022; 41% of articles in 2022 and later), which coincided with the shift towards such narratives in fossil fuel industry messaging mentioned in Sec. I-A.
- While LNG-critical environmental narratives have gained ground since 2022, 18% of articles with an environmental narrative in 2022 or later only contain narratives positive about LNG's environmental impact.
- The majority (66%) of articles where LNG is mentioned as a shipping fuel contain LNG-positive environmental narratives and no LNG-critical environmental narratives. The misrepresentation of LNGs environmental impact is therefore particularly prominent among this subset of articles.
- Considering that the leakage of methane (either during production, transport, or methane slip during combustion) is a large contributor to its climate impact, the fact that only 9.4% of articles with an environmental narrative (and 8.5% of articles which also mention LNG as a shipping fuel) mention methane leaks points to an information gap.
- Experts who are or have been affiliated with the CIEP are cited or consulted more than any other organisation.
- Representatives of lobbies with members in the fossil fuel industry, or organisations which provide lobbying services (public affairs) and have fossil fuel industry clientele, have higher representation than experts cited in articles than spokespeople for environmental organisations.
- The most heavily cited academic was, during the period of study, Manager Corporate Strategy at a fossil fuel company. In the majority of articles where he is cited his company role is not mentioned, but his academic role is.

The following are topics for possible future work:

LNG-critical geopolitical narratives and price narratives: We looked at LNG-positive geopolitical narratives (G+). It would be interesting to also examine LNG-critical geopolitical narratives (G-) and understand how prevalent these are and at what time periods, so that we can compare geopolitical narratives in the same way as we do environmental narratives.

It would also be interesting to investigate narratives relating to LNG's relationship toward gas prices.

Changing industry justifications for LNG: Fossil fuel industry spokespeople have justified the use of LNG in this text corpus in various ways: to reduce flaring, an environmentally harmful practice (mostly in the 1990s, in the context of Shell in Nigeria); because it is a low-carbon fuel; or as a “transition fuel” to pave or smooth the way for other, low-zero carbon fuels, from around 2010 onwards. It would be interesting to map the justifications industry give for the use of a particular technology and examine how they change in response to external factors and public scrutiny.

How Dutch and EU policymakers frame LNG: Policymakers consume media, but are also quoted in media. In our study, we limited ourselves to experts who were not (solely) in politics or in the industry. It would be interesting to see how the actors in the story – policymakers and industry – frame LNG, both in media coverage as well as in parliament.

Impact of media framing on public perception: How does the presentation of LNG in the media affect public attitudes, and how does this vary with factors such as age, political preference, and type or source of media consumed?

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SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS

Due to copyright issues, the article texts cannot be made available, but a list of the articles and their codes can be found at: <http://solid-sustainability.org/LNG-materials>. For help reproducing the results, please contact the authors.

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APPENDIX

A. Appendix A: Table of narratives

LNG-positive				
Safety/ (S+)	Legality	S1	LNG is safe	
		S2	bunkering is allowed	
Innovative (I+)		I1	LNG is part of a growing trend	
		I2	LNG is an Important new technology/pioneering/the future (of shipping)	
Environmental (E+)	E1	Clean(er) fuel	E11	“the cleanest fossil fuel”
			E12	cleaner/better for climate than shipping oil (shipping sector)
			E13	cleaner burning/better for climate than coal or oil (other sectors especially power)
			E14	new technologies/company plans can reduce methane emissions
			E15	can help meet goals/targets for emissions reduction
			E16	political agreements can reduce methane emissions
			E17	Less risky for transport than oil (in terms of spills)
			E18	one sort/provenance of LNG cleaner than another sort/provenance (see also E89)
	E2	Transition fuel	E21	Decarbonisation, road to carbon-neutral, net 0 etc
			E22	Infrastructure can be used in the future for BioLNG, emethane, h2
	E3	Less other emissions	E23	“complement” to renewable fuels
			E31	No sulphur/low NOx emission
			E32	better for air quality
			E33	lower particulate matter
E4	Environmental impact can be offset	E34	reduce environment problems from flaring	
		E41	By protecting corals or other sea life	
		E42	By capturing CO2	
Geopolitical (G+)		G1	Guarantee energy supply, avoid shortages	
		G2	LNG imports mean less political dependence on other countries (who we don't want to depend on)	

Economical/ Pragmatic (P+)	P1	Keep gas prices down		
	P2	export of LNG good for building economy of e.g. Iraq		
	P3	Available at scale		
	P4	Essential for industry (and therefore society)		
	P5	Takes up less space, compact		
	P6	Competitively priced compared to other fuels		
	P7	LNG means diversity of supply, in case pipelines are unable to deliver		
	P8	Efficient fuel		
Ethical (T+)	T1	LNG offers an alternative to buying gas which supports unethical regimes		
LNG-critical				
Safety/ (S-)	Legality	S3	LNG leaks are dangerous	
Geopolitical (G-)	G3	We still get lots of LNG from Russia (hence not independent)		
	G4	LNG comes from other countries we don't want to depend on (e.g. Qatar)		
	G5	European countries hogging LNG means poorer countries have to go back to coal		
	G6	Independence from gas / more renewables is better in the long term		
Economical/ Pragmatic (P-)	P9	Renewables are a more practical/cheaper alternative to fossil fuels		
	PA	Not available for all ships		
	PB	Not readily available at all ports		
	PC	Not actually needed/ overcapacity		
	PD	Expensive		
Environmental (E-)	E5	There are emissions (including of methane) in the production chain	E51	during production (including flaring)
			E52	In transport over land
			E53	During liquefaction or expansion

		E54	In transport over sea, due to: leakage/boil off, to power the ship, turbine slip
E6	Not a transition fuel	E61	creates lock-in, e.g. because of contracts, or an oversupply/ lot of supply
		E62	infrastructure cannot, or is difficult to, be repurposed
E7	still fossil fuel/creates CO2 on combustion		
E8	LNG compared to other fuels	E81	Local fossil fuels more environmentally friendly
		E82	LNG comparable to coal
		E83	LNG worse than coal
		E84	LNG worse than normal gas
		E85	LNG not better than diesel/oil
		E86	Local coal power better than burning LNG
		E87	LNG worse than ammoniac
		E88	LNG is worse than biofuels
		E89	one sort/provenance of LNG worse than another sort/provenance (see also E18)
E9	LNG harmful to surroundings	E91	LNG leaks are harmful to surrounding nature
		E92	Building LNG terminals destroys nature
		E93	Fracking/gas production for LNG is harmful or polluting (without mentioning GHG emissions)
		E94	LNG terminals harm surrounding people/nature
		E95	Transport by ship is dangerous/damaging, also due to degassing
		E96	Flaring harmful to surroundings
EX	LNG not green/clean		
EY	For storage, they need special metals like nickel and aluminium (presented as environmental disadvantage)		
EZ	LNG against climate goals/promises		
Ethical (T-)	T2		LNG comes from countries which don't align with our human rights goals
LNG-neutral			
Safety/legality (S*)	S4		requires crew training, certification and qualification

B. Appendix B: Media outlet list

The news entities that were represented were:

- AD (and subsidiary newspapers)
- Almere Vandaag
- Alphen.cc
- BN/DeStem
- Brabants Dagblad
- DAG
- Dagblad van het Noorden
- De Limburger
- De Stentor (and subsidiary newspapers)
- De Gelderlander
- De Groene Amsterdammer
- De Telegraaf
- De Volkskrant
- De Waalkanter West Maas en Waal
- Elsevier Weekblad
- Eindhovens Dagblad
- Franeker Courant
- Friesch Dagblad
- HP/De Tijd
- Haarlems Dagblad
- Het Financieele Dagblad*
- Het Parool
- Hoogeveensche Courant
- Huis aan Huis Enschede
- IJmuider Courant
- Leeuwarder Courant
- Leidsch Dagblad
- margriet.nl
- Meppeler Courant
- Metronieuws.nl
- Noordhollands Dagblad
- NOS
- NRC
- Nederlands Dagblad
- Nieuwe Ooststellingwerper
- Nieuwsblad Noordoost-Friesland
- PZC
- Quote
- Reformatorisch Dagblad
- Steenwijker Courant
- Stellingwerf
- Trouw
- Tubantia (and subsidiary newspapers)
- Vrij Nederland
- nu.nl

* there are only a few articles from this title, because access is limited via Nexis Uni.

One major online news source was missing: RTL online. Their website was not easily scrapable. According to their web search they had 63 articles on “vloeibaar gas” in the relevant period, which is less than 1% of the corpus.

Note that news outlets are grouped by their current owner/news desk. For example, the *Nieuw Kamper Dagblad* is grouped with *De Stentor*, which took it over in 2003, even for articles before 2003.

Appendix C: Search terms and coding instructions

These were the search terms used to filter articles as in Sec. II-D. Terms are case sensitive. Since regular expressions were not used,

Irrelevant articles: ‘opinie’, ‘lezersbrief’, ‘de rubriek u’, ‘gastbijdrag’, ‘lpg’, ‘vloeibaar waterstof’, ‘autogas’, ‘planeet ontdekt’, ‘kamerlingh onnes’, ‘saturnus’, ‘titan’, ‘zuurstof’,

Shipping fuel: ‘scheepvaart’, ‘varen op’, ‘voor schepen’, ‘aandrij’, ‘aangedreven’, ‘stookolie’, ‘cruisesch’, ‘zeevaart’, ‘rederij’, ‘varende’, ‘scheepsbrandstof’, ‘vaart op’, ‘bunker’

Methane leaks: ‘methaan’, ‘lek’, ‘ontsnap’, ‘vrijkom’, ‘komt vrij’, ‘ch4’, ‘slip’

E+ and E-: ‘schone’, ‘schoon’, ‘fijnstof’, ‘waterstof’, ‘vervuil’, ‘vergroen’, ‘waterstof’, ‘duurzaam’, ‘duurzaam’, ‘overbrugging’, ‘fijnstof’, ‘ombouw’, ‘omgebouw’, ‘transitie’, ‘methaan’, ‘klimaat’, ‘uitstoot’, ‘uitstoot’, ‘co2’, ‘energiedichtheid’, ‘minder schade’, ‘overgang’, ‘milieuvergunning’, ‘fakkel’, ‘milieu’, ‘eerste stap richting’, ‘zwavel’, ‘stikstof’, ‘kooldioxid’, ‘overstap’, ‘groene schip’, ‘zuinig superjacht’, ‘transitiebrandstof’, ‘overgangsbrandstof’, ‘tussenoplossing’

G+: ‘toevoer’, ‘zekerheid’, ‘minder afhankelijk’, ‘onafhankelijk’, ‘import’, ‘voorraad’, ‘voorraden’, ‘sancties’, ‘rusland’, ‘russisch’, ‘oekra’, ‘rantsoen’, ‘capaciteitstekort’, ‘genoeg gas te hebben’, ‘vloeibaar gas hard nodig’, ‘uitschieters in het verbruik’, ‘energiecrisis’, ‘voorziening op peil’, ‘energie schaars’, ‘voldoende vloeibaar gas’, ‘voldoende gas’, ‘gasoorlog’, ‘vervang’, ‘qatar’

Instructions for coding:

(English translation below)

E+ (zonder E2, transitiebrandstof): LNG is schoon, schoner dan andere brandstoffen, of milieuvriendelijk; beleid of technologie kan zijn klimaatimpact verminderen; LNG brengt (milieu)doelen in zicht; LNG vermindert affakkelen; Er zijn dingen die de klimaatimpact van LNG kunnen compenseren, bijv. bescherming van koraalriffen of zeeleven o.a., of afvang van CO2; LNG stoot geen of minder zwavel, stikstof, of fijnstof uit of is beter voor de luchtkwaliteit; schepen of voertuigen die varen/rijden op LNG, zijn milieuvriendelijk.

Niet: LNG is ‘beter’ (zonder nadere toelichting)

E2 (transitiebrandstof): LNG is een transitiebrandstof, overbruggingsbrandstof, of een stap op weg naar een schonere brandstof (of naar netto null, of naar fossielvrij); LNG infrastructuur kan/zal gebruikt of omgebouwd voor een schonere brandstof

Niet: LNG groeit of LNG infrastructuur wordt uitgebreid.

E- (zonder E6, geen transitiebrandstof): Er is uitstoot tijdens productie, transport, liquefactie of hergassing van LNG, of deze zijn vervuילend; LNG is immers een fossiele brandstof/stoot CO2 uit bij verbranding; LNG is slechter dan andere fossiele brandstoffen; LNG, zijn infrastructuur, of zijn ontginning is schadelijk voor het milieu/de omgeving; LNG is niet groen, schoon, of milieuvriendelijk; lagering van LNG is vervuילend of heeft vervuילende processen nodig; LNG is tegen klimaatdoelen/beleid/beloftes.

E6 (geen transitiebrandstof): LNG veroorzaakt “lock-in” of afhankelijkheid (vanwege infrastructuur, overaanbod/veel aanbod), LNG infrastructuur kan niet (makkelijk) verbruikt worden voor schonere brandstoffen (of dit is niet vanzelfsprekend)

G+: LNG draagt bij aan energiezekerheid/leveringszekerheid, is nodig voor genoeg toevoer of voorraad, en voorkomt energietekorten/noodsituaties/crises of dat industrie stilvalt/huizen in de kou komen te staan; LNG kan politieke of strategische afhankelijkheid van andere landen (zoals Rusland) verminderen; LNG wordt voorgesteld als oplossing voor energieproblemen veroorzaakt door sancties (op Rusland) of het stopzetten van gasleveringen om geopolitieke redenen, bijvoorbeeld het invullen van plotselinge tekorten;

Niet: LNG is nodig om de gasprijs te drukken, LNG kan prijsstijgingen of volatiliteit vermijden; LNG toevoer is verhoogd nadat Russisch gas is weggefallen (zonder verdere toelichting); door meer LNG te importeren kan een politiek statement worden gemaakt (tegenover Rusland).

English translation:

E+ (without E2, transition fuel): LNG is clean, cleaner than other fuels, or environmentally friendly; policy or technology can reduce its climate impact; LNG brings (environmental) goals within reach; LNG reduces flaring; There are things that can offset the climate impact of LNG, e.g., protection of coral reefs or marine life, or CO2 capture; LNG emits no or less sulphur, nitrogen, or particulate matter, or is better for air quality; ships or vehicles running on LNG are environmentally friendly.

Not: LNG is ‘better’ (without further explanation).

E2 (transition fuel): LNG is a transition fuel, bridging fuel, or a step towards a cleaner fuel (or towards net zero, or fossil-free); LNG infrastructure can/will be used or converted for a cleaner fuel.

Not: LNG is growing or LNG infrastructure is being expanded.

E- (without E6, not a transition fuel): There are emissions during production, transport, liquefaction, or regasification of LNG, or these are polluting; after all, LNG is a fossil fuel/emits CO₂ when burned; LNG is worse than other fossil fuels; LNG, its infrastructure, or its extraction is harmful to the environment/surroundings; LNG is not green, clean, or environmentally friendly; storage of LNG is polluting or requires polluting processes; LNG is against climate goals/policies/commitments.

E6 (not a transition fuel): LNG causes “lock-in” or dependency (due to infrastructure, oversupply/abundant supply); LNG infrastructure cannot (easily) be used for cleaner fuels (or this is not self-evident).

G+: LNG contributes to energy security or security of supply, is needed for sufficient supply or keeping reserves filled, and prevents energy shortages, emergency situations, crises, industry falling still or homes being cold; LNG can reduce political or strategic dependence on other countries (such as Russia); LNG is presented as a solution for energy problems caused by sanctions (on Russia) or the unforeseen halt of gas deliveries for geopolitical reasons, for example filling sudden shortages.

Not: LNG is needed to lower gas prices, LNG can avoid price increases or volatility; LNG supply has increased after Russian gas fell away (without further explanation); increasing LNG import allows us to make a moral/political statement (to Russia).